

Metallic Titanium in Organic Synthesis.

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In continuation of the work on synthetic use of metals published from this laboratory (Ray and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 103 ; Chakrabarty and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 517 ; Lal and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 565 ; Gaiind and Dutt, *Allahabad University Studies*, 1934, 4, 293 ; Lal and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 389) the metal titanium has now been used for the first time in organic synthesis, since it is now commercially available. The present investigation embodies the results of successful experiments with the metal, while the record of unsuccessful attempts has been avoided for the sake of abbreviation.

As the result of the above investigation it has been found that metallic titanium plays a purely catalytic part in the Zincke's and Friedel and Craft's reactions that have been carried out with the metal, since the yields of the reaction products were found to be independent of the amount of metal used in the reactions. Also a very small amount of the metal was required to start the reaction in most of the reactions. Zincke's reaction gave the most satisfactory result with metallic titanium and the yields obtained in this case were consequently the highest. Ullmann's reaction with metallic titanium was far less satisfactory, and also as in the case of metallic chromium (Chakrabarty and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) titanium also reacted only in those cases where the halogen atom was loosely attached to the organic molecule. Titanium as a neutral reducing agent was also not much of a success. In comparison with the other metals that have been worked up in this laboratory, it has been found that titanium is only slightly more reactive than chromium, but far less reactive than aluminium, thorium or cerium.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Zincke's Reactions with Metallic Titanium.

Action of benzyl chloride on benzene.—A mixture of dry benzene (50 g.), benzyl chloride (24 g.) and titanium (4.5 g.) was refluxed on the water-bath for 10 hours. The reaction began after 2½ hours and

copious hydrogen chloride was evolved during the rest of the period. The filtered product was fractionated at the ordinary and also reduced pressure and three fractions, *viz.*, (a) at 200-270°/755 mm., (b) at 200-250°/50 mm., and (c) at 250-360°/10 mm. were collected. Fraction (a), redistilled at 258-262°, on keeping in a refrigerator, solidified to a mass of radiating needles, m.p. 25-26° and was identified to be diphenylmethane, yield 9.8 g.

Fraction (b) on standing for a few days in the refrigerator, deposited a mass of crystalline matter which on recrystallisation from acetic acid melted at 57° and was identified to be $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -triphenylethane, yield 4.2 g. The mother liquor from the above on dilution with alcohol and allowing it to stand for several days deposited another crop of crystals, m.p. 67-68° which were identified to be *o* dibenzylbenzene, yield 0.5 g. The alcoholic mother liquor from the above on evaporation gave a viscid product from which nothing definite could be isolated.

Fraction (c) was found to be a complex condensation product of indefinite constitution containing chlorine.

Action of benzyl chloride on naphthalene—The reaction was carried on as above and four fractions were collected at 760 mm. (a) up to 250°, (b) at 250-320°, (c) 320-370° and (d) above 370°.

Fraction (a) was mainly benzyl chloride and fraction (b) mainly naphthalene. Fraction (c) was freed from traces of naphthalene by steam distillation and again fractionated, when the greater portion of it came over at 340-355°, and a small portion at 300-320°. Both these fractions solidified on standing and the small fraction on recrystallisation from hot alcohol melted at 39-40°, and was identified to be β -benzyl-naphthalene. The greater fraction was crystallised from methyl alcohol in rhombic plates, m.p. 57-58° and was identified to be α -benzyl-naphthalene. Both these substances on treatment with nitric acid yielded the corresponding phenyl-naphthyl ketone, the α -compound melting at 72-73° and the β -compound at 79-80°. The yield of β -benzyl-naphthalene was 18 g. and that of α -benzyl-naphthalene was 10 g.

Action of benzyl chloride on diphenyl.—The reaction was carried on as usual and the product was extracted with benzene, filtered and the filtrate fractionated at 10 mm. Four fractions were collected (a) up to 100°, (b) 100-200°, (c) 200-250° and (d) 250-360°.

Fraction (a) was mainly benzyl chloride and diphenyl. Fraction (b) was redistilled and the distillate, collected at 150-200°/10 mm.,

was mixed with fraction (c) and distilled once again. The fraction collected at 174-180°/10 mm., was a colourless oil which quickly solidified and on crystallisation from acetic acid was obtained in long glistening white needles, m. p. 44-45°. On oxidation with chromic acid in glacial acetic acid, the substance was converted into terephthalic acid and this together with the fact that on analysis it was found to have a formula $C_{19}H_{16}$ confirmed the substance to be *p*-benzylidiphenyl. No other substance could be isolated from the mother liquors or from the fraction (d), which remained as a non-crystallisable syrup. All the substances isolated in course of this experiment had very strong floral odours. (Found: C, 93·4; H, 6·65. $C_{19}H_{16}$ requires C, 93·44; H, 6·56 per cent). The yield of *p*-benzylidiphenyl was 12·4 g.

Action of benzyl chloride on quinol dimethyl ether.—A mixture of benzyl chloride (15 g.), quinol dimethyl ether (25 g.) and titanium powder (4 g.) was refluxed at 130-140° for 8 hours. The product was treated with dilute caustic soda so as to dissolve any demethylated product and then extracted with benzene. After evaporation of the solvent, the product was fractionated at the ordinary pressure and resolved into five fractions: (a) below 200°, (b) 200-280°, (c) 280-320°, (d) 320-360° and (e) above 360°. Fraction (a) was mainly moisture and benzyl chloride, fraction (b) was quinol dimethyl ether, fraction (c) was a yellow oil changing to deep red on keeping, fraction (d) was a red oil and fraction (e) was a dark red jelly. Fraction (c) on standing for about two months gave a small amount of a pale yellow crystalline substance melting at 104-105°. This product was not noticed by previous workers and was probably dibenzylquinol dimethyl ether, but this could not be confirmed on account of the poor yield. Fraction (d), redistilled at 350-360°, was found to be pure benzylquinol dimethyl ether, yield 23·5 g.

Action of benzyl chloride on anisole.—This reaction was brought about in the same way as the one mentioned above. The product on fractionation above 290° yielded three fractions: (a) 290-315°, (b) 315-345°, and (c) 345-380°. Fraction (a) redistilled at 303-305° was a very large one and was identified to be anisoylphenylmethane. Fraction (b) was a very small one and could not be identified. Fraction (c), redistilled at 376-382°, was a pale yellow liquid with an intense greenish-blue fluorescence and was identified to be 2:4-dibenzylanisole. (Found: C, 86·1; H, 7·3. $C_{21}H_{20}O$ requires C, 87·5; H, 7·1 per cent). Yield of the first product was 63% and that of the second 12%.

Action of benzyl chloride on phenetole.—This reaction was also

carried on in a similar way to the above. The product was fractionated and three fractions isolated: (a) at 305-315°, (b) at 315-345° and (c) at 345-360°. Fractions (a) and (b) were mixed together and redistilled at 330-346° and once again at 338-341°, when a pale yellow oil was obtained which was identified to be *p*-ethoxydiphenylmethane, yield 76%. Fraction (c) was a yellowish red oil which on cooling became semi-solid and was probably *dibenzylphenetole* but this could not be confirmed as the product could not be purified sufficiently for analysis.

Action of benzyl chloride on toluene.—This reaction was carried on in the same way as with benzene. The product was fractionated as usual and four fractions were isolated: (a) at 100-200°, (b) 200-260°, (c) at 260-285° and (d) at 285-360°. Fraction (a) was unchanged benzyl chloride and toluene, fraction (b) was very small and was of indefinite composition, fraction (c), redistilled at 279-290° and once again at 283-287°, was a colourless oil identified to be *p*-benzyltoluene and fraction (d) redistilled at 260-270°/10 mm. was a colourless highly fluorescent oil which appeared to be 2:4-*dibenzyltoluene* from its analysis. (Found: C, 92.4; H, 7.6. $C_{21}H_{20}$ requires C, 92.8, H, 7.2 per cent). (cf. Weber and Zincke, *J. Chem. Soc. Abs.*, 1875, i, 158). Yield of the first product was 12.8 g. and that of the second was 9.2 g.

Action of benzyl chloride on phenol.—The reaction was carried on as usual and the product on fractionation at the ordinary pressure yielded two main fractions: (a) at 310-330° and (b) at 360-380°. Fraction (a), redistilled at 315-325° and once again at 320-322°, was a colourless non-fluorescent oil with a fine flowery smell and giving no colour reaction with aqueous or alcoholic ferric chloride. It solidified on standing in the refrigerator for nearly a month and then crystallised from alcohol in colourless glistening prisms melting at 83° and was identified to be *p*-benzylphenol, yield 10 g. Fraction (b) was found to be insoluble in caustic alkalis and was apparently free from phenolic groups. It was, in all probability, *p*-benzylphenol-benzyl ether but this could not be ascertained for want of authoritative data. It boiled at 364-365° and was a colourless oil with a strong floral odour, yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 87.1; H, 6.8. $C_{20}H_{18}O$ requires C, 87.5, H, 6.5 per cent).

Action of benzyl chloride on acenaphthene.—This reaction which was also a very vigorous one and was carried in a similar way to the above. The product was extracted with benzene and after evaporation of the solvent it was fractionated at a pressure of 10 mm. Four fractions

were collected, (a) at 150-200° a colourless oil, solidifying at once, (b) at 200-250° a trace of an oil partially solidifying, (c) at 250-300° a colourless oil and (d) at 300-360° a red oil. Fraction (a) was only unchanged acenaphthene; fraction (c), redistilled at 260-270°, partially solidified on treatment with twice its volume of alcohol and the separated crystals on recrystallisation from acetic acid melted at 49° and were identified with *α*-benzylacenaphthene (cf. Dwonewaski and Leonbard, *J. Chem. Soc. Abs.*, 1929, *i*, 56). The alcoholic mother liquor from the above on slow evaporation yielded another colourless crystalline substance which on three recrystallisations from acetic acid melted at 110-111° and was identified to be 5-benzylacenaphthene. It gave 5-benzylacenaphthenequinone on oxidation with chromic acid in glacial acetic acid, m. p. 164°, yield of *α*-benzylacenaphthene was 42%.

Friedel and Craft's Reactions with Metallic Titanium.

Benzophenone from benzoyl chloride and benzene.—A mixture of dry benzene (28 g.), benzoyl chloride (20 g.) and titanium powder (4.2 g) was refluxed on the water-bath for 30 hours. The product was fractionated at the ordinary pressure and the fraction boiling at 280-320° and redistilled at 305-315° was collected. It solidified in the receiver and on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 47° and was identified to be benzophenone, yield 4.2 g.

Acetophenone from acetyl chloride and benzene.—The reaction was carried on in a similar way to the above. The yield from 22 g. of benzene and 16 g. of acetyl chloride was only 1.8 g.

Triphenylchloromethane from benzotrichloride and benzene.—A mixture of benzene (30 g.), benzotrichloride (25 g.) and titanium (6 g.) was refluxed on the oil-bath at 130-40° for 10 hours. The product was extracted with carbon disulphide and after the removal of the solvent it was fractionated at 10 mm. The fraction boiling at 200-250° solidified in the receiver and on recrystallisation from alcohol was obtained in the form of pale yellow needles melting at 104° and were identified to be triphenylchloromethane, yield 2.8 g.

Benzoylbenzoic acid from benzoyl chloride and benzoic acid.—A mixture of benzoyl chloride (15 g.), benzoic acid (12 g.) and titanium (5.4 g.) was refluxed at 150-160° for 16 hours. The product was steam distilled to remove the excess of benzoic acid and then treated

with a slight excess of ammonium hydroxide, which completely precipitated the titanium as hydroxide. The filtrate on concentration and subsequent acidification with hydrochloric acid precipitated the benzoylbenzoic acid, m. p. 127°, yield 4.2 g.

Ullmann's Reaction with Titanium Metal.

Diphenyl ether from phenol and bromobenzene.—A mixture of phenol (15 g.), bromobenzene (20 g.), potassium carbonate (5 g.) and titanium was refluxed at 180-200° for 15 hours. The reaction product was filtered and extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with dilute caustic soda. After the removal of the solvent, the product was fractionated and the fraction boiling at 250-252° was isolated. It was a pale yellow oil with a fine flowery odour and was identified to be diphenyl ether, yield 2.4 g.

Diphenylamine from bromobenzene and aniline.—This reaction was carried on in the usual manner and the yield obtained was only about 8% of the theoretical. When iodobenzene was substituted in place of bromobenzene, the yield improved to about 12%.

Succinic acid from sodium chloracetate and sodium acetate.—This reaction was carried on in the same way as in the case of cerium (Lal and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) and the yield obtained was 24%.

Diethyl succinate from ethyl chloracetate and ethyl acetate.—This reaction was carried on in the same way as above and the yield of the reaction product was about 35%.

Hexanitrodiphenyl from picryl chloride.—A mixture of picryl chloride (10 g.) and titanium powder (4 g.), was heated at 140-150° for 15 hours. The product was extracted with benzene, the benzene extract repeatedly washed with a strong solution of caustic soda and then with water until the washings were colourless and finally the benzene was evaporated, when a brownish yellow crystalline mass was obtained. On recrystallisation from alcohol it was obtained in bright yellow needles, m. p. 238° and was identified to be hexanitrodiphenyl, yield was only 0.91 g.

Reformatsky's reaction with titanium powder.—This reaction was carried on in the same way as in the case of cerium (Lal and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) with acetophenone and bromoacetic ester and the product identified to be β -phenylmethyl hydroxypropionic ester, yield 2.1 g.

Neutral reduction with titanium powder.—Neutral reductions with titanium powder were not very satisfactory, since in each case the yield was very low. The reductions were carried on according to the method of Lal and Dutt.

Picramic acid from picric acid.—The yield was only 0.5 g. from 2 g. of picric acid. *Benzhydrol from benzophenone.*—The yield was 0.66 g. from 2 g. of benzophenone. *o-Aminophenol from o-nitrophenol.*—Yield was 0.2 g. from 2 g. *Aniline from nitrobenzene.*—The yield was 3 g. from 10 g.

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Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part IV. The Structure of Aliphatic Diazo-compounds.

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In spite of much work done by various investigators for more than fifty years, the constitution of the aliphatic diazo-compounds has not yet been definitely settled. Curtius (*Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2230), who discovered these compounds, proposed the structure (I) while Angeli (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1907, *ii* **16**, 790) first pointed out that the reactions of these compounds are best represented by the structure (II)

(I)

(II)

which was further advocated by Thiele (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 2552). Both the ring structure of Curtius and the open-chain structure of Angeli-Thiele, have been supported by different investigators from time to time, and it is not possible from a perusal of the literature on the subject to arrive at a definite conclusion. The reactions which these compounds undergo can be explained equally well by means of either the Curtius or the Angeli-Thiele formula. These facts led the present author to attempt at a solution of the problem by determining the parachor of these compounds, the difference in the parachor between the two forms being sufficiently large for a definite decision to be possible by each measurement. It was noted by many investiga-